

Speculation on the Maximum Entropy Approach

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The Maximum Entropy Approach often postulates a function $F(p(e_i))$ such that its average, often given by $\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$, when maximized subject to constraints yields a minimum information probability distribution $p(e_i)$. We try to understand why such an approach should be used from a minimal information point of view. In other words, we try to determine why one should consider $\sum_i p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$ in the first place. In general, it does not seem like something one would write a priori.

First, we argue that one often uses moments for constraints. In particular, two common constraints are: $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$. Then $N \cdot E_{ave}$ (N =number of particles) is E_{total} which is a reasonable known physical value. We argue that by using these moment constraints, one is approximating a physical system statistically. (For example, a class may be described by an average test score.)

The immediate problem, however, is that any $p(e_i)$ set can usually be normalized and that one may have many $\{p(e_i)\}$ sets which yield the same average energy. In fact, given one $\{p(e_i)\}$, one may easily create another $\{p(e_i) + dp(e_i)\}$ which is normalized and yields the same E_{ave} . This begs the question: What $p(e_i)$ should be used? One might argue that the minimal information one is the choice, but how does one find minimal information? We first suggest that describing a problem in terms of both $p(e_i)$ and the moments e_i power 1 and e_i power 0 means writing two sets of information. One could try to consolidate these two pieces of information by introducing a function $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T + b$. One cannot have more moment information because $p F(p)$ is supposed to describe the statistical approximation to the physical system (i.e. be equivalent to the constraint approach) except that it consolidates information by only using $p(e_i)$ as the variables and not e_i , 1 and $p(e_i)$ as the constraints do. One might argue that F and p are also two sets of information, but they are the inverse of each other.

The main idea is that by consolidating information into the $p(e_i)F(p(e_i))$ form and comparing with the constraint form when $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$, one obtains a condition on $F(p(e_i))$. If one knows $F(p(e_i))$, one knows $p(e_i)$. We argue that if $p(e_i)$ and $p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ are both solutions for the same constraint set, then one should have $F(p(e_i))$ and $F(p(e_i) + dp(e_i))$. The catch is that changing $p(e_i)$ to $p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ in the constraints does not involve any functional information because one has two sets of information, $p(e_i)$ and the constraint moment pieces e_i and e_i power 0. By writing $F(p(e_i))$ or $F(p(e_i) + dp(e_i))$, one must deal with changes to both $p(e_i)$ and $F \rightarrow p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ and F . The reason that one wrote $F(p(e_i))$ in the first place is to consolidate information.

Now $F(p + dp) = F(p) + dp \frac{dF}{dp}$ to first order. This must match the constraint change $e_i (p + dp) + b (p + dp)$. Thus, F must be of the form $F = \frac{1}{p} + b$ to first order leaving $\frac{dF}{dp}$ which is not of the form dp found in the constraints. Now $\frac{dF}{dp}$ is multiplied by dp and so one must use $\frac{dF}{dp} = \frac{dF}{dp}$ to first order. By consolidating information in one variable $p(e_i)$ and using $F(p(e_i))$ one has a condition on $\frac{dF}{dp}$ because $p \frac{dF}{dp} dp(e_i)$ either equals a constant or $(a_1 e_i + a_2) dp(e_i)$. The choices are $\frac{dF}{dp} = 1$ seems to be a viable choice, otherwise one would use $p \frac{dF}{dp} = a_1 F + a_2$. $\frac{dF}{dp} = 1$ leads to $\ln(p) = F$ for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, i.e. leads to a unique solution for p . The second choice leads to a Tsallis form. This solution arises when one tries to consolidate

information by having $F(p)$ contain both p and the moments e_i and e_i power 1. This approach shows that one cannot have $p(e_i)$ and $p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ as viable solutions, but must have a $p(e_i)$ such that $p \rightarrow p + dp(e_i)$ leads to the extremization of $pF(p)$ which might be called information theory information.

Approximating a Physical System Statically

Approximating a physical system statistically is often done in real life, often by using average moments of some variable. For example, one might use the average test score for a class. If one has a gas of N particles, physically it should have a total energy. One might suggest a probability $p(e_i)$ for a single particle to have energy e_i and then use the two moments:

$$\sum_i p(e_i) = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}} \quad \text{such that} \quad N \cdot E_{\text{ave}} = E_{\text{total}} \quad ((2))$$

The problem with this approach for a gas is that one has no a priori idea what $p(e_i)$ is because there are many $p(e_i)$ sets which satisfy ((2)). To see this, one may consider a set $\{ p(e_i) \}$ which satisfies ((2)) and easily change it to $\{ p(e_i) + dp(e_i) \}$, which also satisfies ((2)). Which set does one choose? One might argue for a minimal information set, but it is not clear at this point what that means.

In order to try to define a minimal information approach we first note that the constraints ((2)) are expressed in terms of two sets of information $p(e_i)$ and the moments e_i power 0 and e_i power 1. One might suggest that these two pieces of information may be combined into a single function:

$$F(p(e_i)) * p(e_i) \quad \text{such that} \quad F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T + b \quad (\text{where } -1/T \text{ and } b \text{ are constant}) \quad ((3))$$

F is the inverse of $p(e_i)$, but $p(e_i)$ is still completely unknown. All one has done is try to consolidate information into $p(e_i)$ (because F is its inverse) while $p(e_i)$ and e_i power 0, and e_i power 1 are two sets of information.

The issue which arises with the constraint form ((2)) is that a set $\{ p(e_i) \}$ and $\{ p(e_i) + dp(e_i) \}$ both satisfy ((2)). One may see what happens with the consolidated information form $p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$.

Given that one has two sets $\{ p(e_i) \}$ and $\{ p(e_i) + dp(e_i) \}$, there should be two separate inverse functions F and F_1 .

$$F(p) = -e_i/T + b \quad (\text{from the constraints}) \quad ((4a))$$

$$F_1(p + dp) = -e_i/T + b \quad ((4b))$$

One may expand ((4b)) to

$$F_1(p) = -e_i/T + b \quad \text{and} \quad p \frac{dF_1}{dp} = \text{constant} \quad \text{or} \quad a_1 e_i + a_2 \quad (a_1, a_2 \text{ are constants}) \quad ((5))$$

To first order the functional form F must be F in both $F(p)$ and dF/dp because $p dF/dp$ is multiplied by dp .

If $p dF/dp = 1$, then $F = \ln(p)$ or $p = \exp(-e_i/T) C$ ((6)) which is the Maxwell-Boltzmann solution.

The alternative $p dF/dp = a_1 e_i + a_2 = a_3 F + a_4$ or $\ln(p) = 1/a_3 \ln(a_3 F + a_4)$ or

$p^{a_3} = a_3 F + a_4$ or $F = 1/a_3 \{ p^{a_3} + a_4 \}$ ((6))

This is of the general form of a Tsallis distribution.

In other words, by consolidating the two pieces of information $p(e_i)$ and the moments e_i power 0 and e_i power 1 in the constraints into $F(p)$ (where F is the inverse of p), changing $p \rightarrow p+dp$ has consequences on the form of F and allows one to find a specific form for F . If one only considers the constraints $p(e_i)$ and $p(e_i)+dp(e_i)$ are equally good solutions, but in the consolidated case $p F(p(e_i))$, a change in $p(e_i)$ to $p(e_i) + dp(e_i)$ leads to a new F inverse function which is F to first order and so expanding in $dp(e_i)$ and comparing with the constraint in terms of $p(e_i)+dp(e_i)$ leads to a condition for $p dF/dp$ because $F(p)$ is already taken to be of the form of the constraint $-e_i/T+b$.

Mathematically, this is equivalent to maximizing $p F(p)$ subject to the constraints, but we argue that the underlying idea is to consolidate the two pieces of information in the constraint, $p(e_i)$ and the moments e_i power 0, e_i power 1 into one piece $p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$. This consolidated form cannot change at will like the constraint form as it is consolidated and this gives rise to a condition on $p dF/dp$. We show that if this is 1, one obtains a Maxwell-Boltzmann type solution, while if it is $a_1 e_i + a_2$, one obtains a Tsallis result.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we suggest that constraints used for describing a physical system such as a gas represent a statistical approximation. One often uses the moments e_i power 0 and e_i power 1, i.e. $\sum_i p(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i p(e_i) = E_{ave}$, where $E_{ave} * N = E_{total}$ and N is the number of particles. The problem is that many $\{ p(e_i) \}$ sets satisfy these constraints. One might seek a minimal information set, but one must first define what information means. We suggest that using $p(e_i)$ and e_i power 0, e_i power 1 represents two sets of information which may be consolidated into one using $p(e_i) F(p(e_i))$. One might at first think that F and $p(e_i)$ represent two sets of information, but F is the inverse of $p(e_i)$. Given that both descriptions must be the same, $F(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T + b$ (from the constraints). The catch is that the two sets of information constraints are too loose in terms of $p(e_i) \rightarrow p(e_i)+dp(e_i)$, while the consolidated information $p(e_i)F(p(e_i))$ is tighter. This leads to a condition on $p dF/dp$. It may be either a constant (leading to the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution) or $a_1 e_i + a_2$, leading to a Tsallis distribution.